

Studies on magnetic behavior of the yttrium barium copper oxide sample obtained from polymeric precursor technique

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Abstract : It was possible to achieve yttrium barium copper oxide ($Y_1Ba_2Cu_4O_8$) by polymeric precursor technique using sodium polyacrylate. In this present investigation, material obtained by polymeric precursor technique, is washed with distilled water for several times, dried and magnetic measurements have been carried out. It has been found that ferromagnetic behavior is indicated at 77 K and XRD study indicates presence of $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ with some impurity. Moment vs temperature plot shows magnetic nature even near about at 300 K. So the material may be useful. $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ in the material is expected to contribute in magnetic behavior. SEM image indicates different phases. Chemical analysis has been done by EDS which indicates presence of Y, Ba, Cu, O and very little amount of Na.

Keywords : Polymeric precursor, polyvalent metal ion, X-ray diffraction study, magnetic material.

Introduction

Aqueous solution of guar gum-graft-acrylamide (G-g-Am) has been found to bind polyvalent metal ions at different pH range¹. COO^- groups are mainly responsible for binding polyvalent metal ion by G-g-Am²⁻⁴. So sodium polyacrylate may be the better choice. Sodium polyacrylate has been used to prepare yttrium barium copper oxide ($Y_1Ba_2Cu_4O_8$) by polymeric precursor technique⁵. Although material contains impurity. So material obtained is washed with distilled water for several times, dried and submitted for magnetic measurements and then for X-ray diffraction (XRD) study. Magnetic measurements show indication of ferromagnetic behavior at 77 K. Thus this material may be useful. XRD study indicates presence of $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ (superconducting material), along with some impurity. Chemical analysis of the sample is done by EDS and SEM image indicates presence of different phases.

Materials and brief methods :

Preparation of sample :

Yttrium barium copper oxide has been prepared by polymeric precursor technique using aqueous solution of sodium polyacrylate, $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution, $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution and $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution and raising pH by NaOH solution to get precipitate. To remove polymeric part,

material is heated to 1000 °C for 1 h in presence of air. Technique has been reported already in Journal of the Indian Chemical Society⁵. XRD study with the material obtained in this process indicated presence of $Y_1Ba_2Cu_4O_8$ with impurity⁵. In this present investigation material is washed with distilled water for several times and when washing does not give heavy white precipitate by adding potassium pyroantimonate solution (to check Na^+), it is dried and then submitted for magnetic measurements and then for XRD and then for SEM and EDS.

Magnetic measurements :

MPMS SQUID VSM (Magnetic Property Measurement System using Superconducting Quantum Interference Device and Vibrating Sample Magnetometer) has been used to check magnetic properties. Approximately 2.7 mg sample is used for magnetic measurements. Sample is cooled in zero field from 300 K to 5 K. A field (200 oersted) is imposed to get curve for zero field cooling and curve for high field cooling. For zero field cooling curve, temperature is increased from 5 K to 300 K and for field cooling curve; temperature is decreased from 300 K to 5 K.

In moment vs field case, set temperature was 77 K and following variations are considered.

0 → 3000 oersted
 3000 oersted → 50000 oersted
 50000 oersted → 3000 oersted
 3000 oersted → -3000 oersted
 -3000 oersted → -50000 oersted
 -50000 oersted → -3000 oersted
 -3000 oersted → 3000 oersted
 3000 oersted → 50000 oersted

XRD :

XRD study has been carried out with powdered sample using the instrument X' Part PRO [Company → PANalytical (Holland)], target was copper and with low angle proportional detector.

SEM and EDS :

Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) experiment and Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) for % analysis have been carried using SCANNING MICROSCOPE (JEOL Company made in Japan) model number JSM 5800. For SEM, gold coated sample has been used. Gold coating has been done by SPUTTERING TECHNIQUE. For

EDS, sample has not been gold coated and EDS study has been carried out using Oxford Instruments (INCA Software).

Results and discussion

XRD :

XRD pattern of the sample is shown in Fig. 1. Many peaks match with yttrium barium copper oxide [chemical formula $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ (orthorhombic) superconducting material, RI factor (RIR) → 4.06]. Better matching is considered from greater number of matched peaks. Some peaks match with barium oxide and some peaks match with sodium oxide. Positions of the peaks matching with $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ are shown in Fig. 2. Positions of the peaks matching with barium oxide are shown in Fig. 3 and positions of the peaks matching with sodium oxide are shown in Fig. 4. It is expected that $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ will contribute in showing magnetic behavior.

SEM and EDS :

SEM image of the sample has been shown in Fig. 5. SEM image indicates presence of various phases. It contains agglomerates, rod-like phase etc.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of the material obtained after washing and drying.

Fig. 2. Positions of the peaks matching with Y₁Ba₂Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}.

Fig. 3. Positions of the peaks matching with barium oxide.

Fig. 4. Positions of the peaks matching with sodium oxide.

Fig. 5. SEM image for the gold coated sample ($\times 3000$ magnification).

Bulk EDS study indicates presence of the following atoms in the sample :

Atom	Wt%
O	25.29 ± 2.81
Na	2.65 ± 1.57
Cu	22.64 ± 2.52
Y	22.64 ± 2.67
Ba	26.79 ± 2.44

EDS study indicates agglomerates (white) (Fig. 6) mainly contain Y, Ba, Cu and O (Fig. 8) (Table 1).

Thick rod-like phase (Fig. 7) contains mainly Ba and O (Fig. 9) (Table 2).

Grey agglomerate (Fig. 10) mainly contains barium and oxygen (Fig. 11) (Table 3). Presence of Na in the sample is very small.

Fig. 6. White agglomerate for EDS.

Fig. 7. Analysis for white agglomerate (Spectrum 8) by EDS.

Table 1

Element	Weight%	Atomic%
O K	31.15	70.12
Na K	0.23	0.37
Cu K	19.45	11.02
Y L	39.14	15.85
Ba L	10.03	2.63
Total	100.00	

Table 2

Element	Weight%	Atomic%
O K	39.60	78.79
Cu K	18.69	9.37
Y L	17.28	6.19
Ba L	24.43	5.66
Total	100.00	

Fig. 8. Thick rod-like phase for EDS.

Fig. 9. Analysis for thick rod-like phase (Spectrum 5) by EDS.

Fig. 10. Grey agglomerate for EDS.

Fig. 11. Analysis for grey agglomerate (Spectrum 9) by EDS.

Table 3

Element	Weight%	Atomic %
O K	16.09	59.08
Na K	1.91	4.89
Cu K	1.95	1.81
Ba L	80.04	34.23
Total	100.00	

Magnetic measurements :

Moment vs temperature plots are shown in Fig. 12. Symbol of magnetic dipole moment in emu, Gau is erg G^{-1} (where $\text{G} \Rightarrow \text{Gauss}$).

$1 \text{ erg G}^{-1} = 10 \text{ Acm}^2 = 10^{-3} \text{ JT}^{-1}$ (where $\text{T} \Rightarrow \text{Tesla}$)

Again symbol of magnetic dipole moment in Bohr magneton is μ_B .

$$1 \mu_B = 9.27402 \times 10^{-24} \text{ JT}^{-1} = 0.927 \times 10^{-20} \text{ erg G}^{-1}$$

$$1 \text{ G} = 10^{-4} \text{ T} \Rightarrow 1 \text{ Oersted}$$

In Fig. 12 at near about 300 K, there is bifurcation of two curves : curve for zero field cooling (i) and curve for field cooling (ii). This is probably due to difference in alignments in two cases. In zero field cooling [curve (i)], temperature is increased from very low value of temperature. At very low temperature, there may be freezing of the magnetic centers and they may not align quickly when temperature is raised. But after 300 K, when temperature is lowered [curve (ii)], there may be better alignment for the same temperature for two cases : for zero field cooling curve and for field cooling curve. So this indicates, sample shows magnetic nature even near about at 300 K.

At set temperature 77 K, in moment vs field plot (Fig. 13), material is behaving as a ferromagnetic sub-

Fig. 12. Moment vs temperature plots : (i) curve for zero field cooling and (ii) curve for field cooling.

Fig. 13. Moment vs field plot at set temperature 77 K.

stance. Moment vs field plot is not a straight line. This indicates material is ferromagnetic at 77 K and ferromagnetic material generally shows hysteresis loop. So the plot will not be a straight line. 77 K is chosen because $Y_1Ba_2Cu_3O_{7-x}$ shows superconductivity at 77 K.

Analogous to grain boundaries, the magnetic domain walls tend to get pinned down by impurity atoms. Soft magnetic materials should be free of impurities. Usually, there are easy and hard magnetization directions in a crystal. In the manufacture of ceramic magnets by powder compacting, a field is superimposed across the die cavity before pressing, so that the crystalline particles of the powder orient themselves along directions of easy magnetization. Hard magnetic materials are used to produce permanent magnets. Among the metallic alloys, best known are the alnico alloys. These alloys are directionally solidified and subsequently given a heat treatment in a magnetic field that enhances the desired properties. The heat treatment at 800 °C is known to result in a phase separation into two phases of different compositions with differ-

ent amounts of magnetization. The phase with a larger magnetization precipitates in a very fine elongated particles embedded in the matrix of the other phase. In fine particle permanent magnets, particle thickness is smaller than the domain wall thickness so that each one of the particles is a single domain. These particles are embedded in a nonmagnetic resin matrix such that they are separated from one another and remain single domains. Among the nonmetallic oxides used as permanent magnets is the barium ferrite ($BaO.6Fe_2O_3$).

Conclusion :

Work on ceramic magnet is important in Materials Science. This work indicates material obtained by polymeric precursor technique as reported earlier⁵, on washing with distilled water and drying, helps to give a material with ferromagnetic nature at 77 K. So its crystal structure is important. Analysis on XRD indicates $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ is a superconducting material and orthorhombic. So this work may open a new area in research for preparation of superconducting material by polymeric precursor technique. SEM study indicates ma-

terial contains various phases EDS indicates probably these phases are mainly Y-Ba-Cu-O and BaO. Elemental analysis indicates, sodium is present in very small amount.

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